

EXPLORING THE LINK BETWEEN SOCIO-ECONOMIC CONDITIONS AND CRIME: EVIDENCE FROM GARHI KHAIRO, PAKISTAN

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15461565>

Keywords

Crime rate, Socioeconomic factors, Poverty, Unemployment, Community perception.

Article History

Received on 10 April 2025

Accepted on 10 May 2025

Published on 19 May 2025

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Abstract

This study explores the relationship between socio-economic conditions and rising crime in Garhi Khairo, a town in Jacobabad District, Sindh, Pakistan. Residents of the area have expressed growing concern over safety and the effectiveness of law enforcement. The research aims to identify the root causes of crime, focusing on community perceptions and socio-economic factors. Data was collected through structured interviews and questionnaires based on selected variables, supported by literature review. Findings reveal that poverty and unemployment significantly impact crime rates. However, lack of education, drug abuse, and weak law enforcement were found to have no statistically significant effect. The study is limited to Garhi Khairo and may not represent wider regional patterns. It concludes that targeted socio-economic interventions addressing poverty and unemployment could be effective in reducing crime in the area, while other assumed factors need reevaluation.

INTRODUCTION

Crime is a general socioeconomic problem that affects people on a personal, society and societal level. Residents of Garhi Khairo, a town in district Jacobabad Sindh Pakistan is very worried about the trend of increased crime in recent years. In addition to supporting a climate of fear and insecurity, an increase in criminal activity has led to concerns about the efficiency of current law enforcement strategies. With the goal of examining the root causes, effects, and community views of increasing crime in Garhi Khairo, this case study offer useful information that policymakers, law enforcement organizations, and other stakeholders can use to

create focused interventions and long-lasting solutions to deal with this critical social issue.

In-depth investigations that explore the particular problems identified by the people of Garhi Khairo, the causes of the increase in crime, and the efficacy of current crime-prevention methods are hard to come by. It could be difficult for local lawmakers and law enforcement organizations to put effective ideas into practice without having a solid understanding of these dynamics. In order to provide useful ideas to improve public safety and community well-being, this thesis will examine the primary causes of the rising crime in Garhi Khairo, evaluate the worries of the

residents, and analyze the effectiveness of the current crime control strategies.

It is important to understand the worries of the residents of Garhi Khairo in order to create measures that effectively reduce crime and improve community relations. Through focusing on the particular problems that this community faces, the research add to the larger discussions about reducing crime in similar areas. In addition, it offers useful information to law enforcement organizations, legislators, and community leaders who are dealing with the problems caused on by an increase in crime.

Operational definitions:

Poverty: According to income surveys taken throughout the community over the past year, the ratio of people or households in Garhi Khairo living below the commonly recognized poverty level. This definition clearly defines how poverty will be measured and provides an exact level making it measurable and so directly relevant to the research.

Unemployment: According to local labor force surveys, the percentage of Garhi Khairo's working-age population actively looking for job but unable to find work within the previous six months. It makes unemployment measurable in the framework of the research by clearly identifying the age group, duration of time, and the condition of actively looking for employment.

Drug Abuse: According to self-reported surveys and an analysis of drug-related hospital visits or police records over the past 12 months, Garhi Khairo residents regularly take illegal substances or abuse conventional drugs. It makes clear how drug addiction will be recognized and how it will be analyzed, therefore making the study particular and quantitative.

Lack of Education: According to local educational records and last year community surveys, the percentage of Garhi Khairo residents aged 18 and above who have not finished their basic education. It defines the age range and educational level as well as the method of data collecting, therefore making the variable measurable in the framework of the research.

Lack of law enforcement: The percentage of unsolved or uninvestigated crimes based on police records over the past year, the ratio of police officers

to population, and the response times to reported incidents show how ineffective Garhi Khairo's law enforcement agencies are at preventing, responding to, and solving crimes. Because of this definition, which provides identifiable signs, the idea of "lack of law enforcement" may be measured for the reason of the study.

Social Control Theory: According to studies, the social control theory explains why delinquent acts emerge because of a person's commitment to school and school-related activities including homework, respect for teachers, and adherence to class or school norms. Travis Hirschi created this theory, commonly referred to as the social bond theory, in 1969.

Anomie theory: Anomie is defined as the absence of accepted moral or social norms. French sociologist Emile Durkheim introduced this idea for the first time in 1893. When the system has failed and there is uncertainty about what is expected of people, it is called normlessness. When certain persons or entire groups are denied access to these objectives, anomie sets in. Deviant conduct as a result exhibits characteristics of creativity, ritualism, retreat, revolt, and conformity. Emile Durkheim gave this theory in 1893.

Strain theory: According to the theory, those who are poor may feel a great deal of anxiety or tension because they don't have the legal means to achieve societal objectives like social standing or financial success. They may turn to deviant behavior in an attempt to cope with or get over their trying circumstances as a result of this tension. Robert King Merton created this hypothesis in 1938.

Social disorganization theory: According to social disorganization theory, locations with particular environmental conditions—such as extreme unemployment, population changes, or material decay—have constant crime rates. These circumstances reduce community cohesion and social structure, which in turn impacts informal social control of criminality. In 1942, Clifford Shaw and Henry D. McKay proposed this theory.

Hypotheses:

1. **Null Hypothesis (H₀₁):** there is no significant relationship between victimization status and the belief that the crime is caused by poverty.

Alternative Hypothesis (H₁): there is a significant relationship between victimization status and belief that crime is caused by poverty.

2. **Null Hypothesis (H₀₂):** there is no significant relationship between victimization status and the belief that the crime is caused by unemployment.

Alternative Hypothesis (H₂): there is a significant relationship between victimization status and belief that crime is caused by unemployment.

3. **Null Hypothesis (H₀₃):** there is no significant relationship between victimization status and the belief that the crime is caused by lack of education.

Alternative Hypothesis (H₃): there is a significant relationship between victimization status and belief that crime is caused by lack of education.

4. **Null hypothesis (H₀₄):** there is no significant relationship between victimization status and belief that the crime is caused by drug abuse.

Alternative hypothesis (H₄): there is a significant relationship between victimization status and belief that crime is caused by drug abuse.

5. **Null Hypothesis (H₀₅):** there is no significant relationship between victimization status and the belief that the crime is caused by inadequate law enforcement.

Alternative Hypothesis (H₅): there is a significant relationship between victimization status and belief that crime is caused by inadequate law enforcement.

Population:

The study population consists of citizens of Garhi Khairo, including individuals from various socioeconomic backgrounds, local business owners,

law enforcement officers, community leaders, and crime victims.

Sample:

In this study, a total of 75 citizens of Garhi Khairo were interviewed, including business owners, community leaders, and crime victims. Uneducated individuals were excluded from the sample.

Tool:

A 40-item tool was developed by the researcher, based on variables identified through a literature review of related studies. The tool included 19 items for the variable "lack of law enforcement," 3 for "substance use," 4 for "unemployment," 3 for "poverty," and 2 for "lack of education." Each interview lasted approximately 20 minutes and was conducted in suitable locations such as offices, homes, and hotels to ensure a disturbance-free environment.

Statistical Analysis:

To examine the relationship between selected socio-economic variables and public perceptions regarding the causes of crime, the Chi-square test of independence was employed as the primary statistical tool. This non-parametric test is suitable for determining whether there is a significant association between two categorical variables.

For each hypothesis, the observed frequencies collected from the survey responses were compared with the expected frequencies under the assumption of independence. The Chi-square statistic was then calculated for each variable pair.

The calculated Chi-square values were compared against the critical value derived from the Chi-square distribution table, based on the appropriate degrees of freedom and a significance level of 0.05 (5%). If the calculated value exceeded the critical value, the null hypothesis (indicating no relationship) was rejected, suggesting a statistically significant association between the variables. Conversely, if the calculated value was less than the critical value, the null hypothesis was not rejected, implying no statistically significant relationship.

This approach allowed for a systematic evaluation of factors perceived as contributing causes of crime, particularly in relation to individuals' victimization status.

Research frame work:

Data Analysis:

Table 01: Frequency and percentage distribution by age of respondents

Age	Frequency	Percentage
18-25	9	12%
26-33	15	20%
34-41	14	19%
42-49	16	21%
50- More	21	28%
Total	75	100%

The largest portion of respondents (28%) were aged 50 years or older. (21%) were between 42 and 49 years old. About 20% of respondents were aged 26

to 33 years, while 19% were between 34 and 41 years old. The remaining 12% of respondents were between 18 and 25 years of age.

Figure 1: Graphical representation of respondents by age

Table 02: Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents by gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	75	100%
female	0	0%
Total	75	100%

The study shows that all of the respondents were male. No any other gender was interviewed.

The total number of respondents was 75.

Figure 2: Graphical representation of respondents by gender

Table 03: Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents by education

Educational qualification	Frequency	Percentage
Less than Matric	0	0%
Matric	0	0%
Intermediate	27	36%
Graduation	38	51%
Post Graduate	10	13%
Total	75	100%

The study primarily engaged individuals with at least an intermediate level of education, which may influence their perceptions and responses to the subject under investigation. The total number of respondents was 75. The data reveals that the

majority of respondents (51%) were graduates. A significant portion (36%) had completed their intermediate education, while 13% held postgraduate degrees.

Figure 3: Graphical representation of respondents by level of education

Table 04: Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents by employment status

Employment Status	Frequency	Percentage
Unemployed	17	23%
Employed	45	60%
Self Employed	13	17%
Total	75	100%

This distribution shows that most participants were actively engaged in formal or informal work, which may influence their views and experiences related to the study topic. The data indicates that a majority of the respondents (60%) were employed at the time of

the study, suggesting a strong representation from the working population. A smaller proportion (23%) were unemployed, while 17% identified as self-employed.

Figure 4: Graphical representation of respondents by employment status

Table 05: Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents by occupation

Occupation	Frequency	Percentage
Teacher	17	23%
Banker	10	13%
Doctor	10	13%
Farmer	3	4%
Businessman	12	16%
Unemployed	17	23%
Police	6	8%
Total	75	100%

The occupational data shows that the largest groups of respondents were teachers and unemployed individuals, each comprising 23% of the sample. Businessmen made up 16% of the respondents, while bankers and doctors each accounted for 13%, indicating a notable presence from both the financial and healthcare sectors. Police personnel represented

8% of the sample, and farmers were the least represented group at 4%. Overall, the data reflects a diverse occupational background among the 75 respondents, contributing to a broad perspective in the study.

Figure 5: Graphical representation according to occupation of the respondents

Table 06: Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents by monthly income

Monthly income	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 50,000	20	27%
50,000-100,000	37	49%
More than 100,000	13	17%
No income	17	23%
Total	75	100%

The data shows that nearly half of the respondents (49%) reported a monthly income between PKR 50,000 and 100,000, making it the most common income range among participants. Around 27% earned less than PKR 50,000, while 17% had a monthly income exceeding PKR 100,000, indicating a smaller proportion of high earners. Additionally, 23% of respondents reported having no income, which may include students, unemployed individuals, or dependents. Overall, the income distribution suggests a predominance of middle-income earners within the sample of 75 respondents.

Figure 6: Graphical representation of respondents by monthly income

Table 07: Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents based on their concern about the crime rate in the city

Concern level regarding crime rate in the city	Frequency	Percentage
Extremely Concerned	56	74%
Very Concerned	15	20%
Moderately Concerned	4	6%
Slightly Concerned	0	0%
Not At All Concerned	0	0%
Total	75	100%

The data indicates that a significant majority of respondents, 74%, were extremely concerned about the crime rate in their city. Additionally, 20% of respondents were very concerned, while a smaller portion, 6%, were moderately concerned. Notably,

no respondents reported being slightly concerned or not at all concerned. This reflects a high level of public anxiety about crime among the 75 participants, underscoring the importance of addressing safety and security issues in the city.

Figure 7: Graphical representation of respondents according to their concern about the crime rate

Table 08: Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents by their perception of the property crime situation in the city

Situation of property crime in the city	Frequency	Percentage
Extremely problematic	26	34%
Very much problematic	9	12%
Moderately problematic	30	40%
Slightly problematic	10	14%
Not at all problematic	0	0%
Total	75	100%

The data reveals that a significant portion of respondents, 40%, perceive the situation of property crime in the city as moderately problematic. About 34% consider it extremely problematic, highlighting considerable concern among the population. Additionally, 14% view property crime as slightly problematic, while 12% believe it to be very much

problematic. No respondents reported that property crime was not at all problematic. Overall, these findings suggest widespread concern about property crime, with the majority of the 75 respondents acknowledging it as an issue of varying severity.

Figure 8: Graphical representation of respondents by their perception of the property crime situation in the city

Table 09: Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents by their perception of street crime in the city

Situation of street crimes in the city	Frequency	Percentage
Extremely problematic	53	70%
Very much problematic	7	10%
Moderately problematic	5	6%
Slightly problematic	10	14%
Not at all problematic	0	0%
TOTAL	75	100%

The data indicates that the largest portion of respondents (70%) perceive street crimes in the city as extremely problematic. Following this, 14% view the situation as slightly problematic, while 10% consider it very much problematic. A smaller percentage, 6%, regard street crime as moderately

problematic. No respondents felt that street crime was not at all problematic. These findings highlight a strong public concern about street crime, emphasizing the need for effective measures to address safety in the city among the 75 participants.

Figure 9: Graphical representation of respondents by their perception of street crime in the city

Table 10: Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents according to their perception of crimes against individuals in the city

Perception of crime against individuals in the city	Frequency	Percentage
Extremely problematic	45	60%
Very much problematic	20	28%
Moderately problematic	5	6%
Slightly problematic	5	6%
Not at all problematic	0	0%
Total	75	100%

The data shows that a majority of respondents (60%) perceive crime against individuals in the city as extremely problematic. An additional 28% consider it very much problematic, indicating a high level of concern among the population. Smaller proportions of respondents view the situation as moderately

problematic (6%) or slightly problematic (6%), while none believe that crime against individuals is not at all problematic. These findings highlight a significant public awareness and concern regarding personal safety in the city among the 75 respondents.

Figure 10: Graphical representation of respondents according to their perception of crimes against individuals in the city

Table 11: Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents according to their perception regarding violent crimes in the city

Situation of violent crimes in the city	Frequency	Percentage
Extremely problematic	29	39%
Very much problematic	15	20%
Moderately problematic	26	34%
Slightly problematic	5	7%
Not at all problematic	0	0%
Total	75	100%

The data shows that the largest portion of respondents (39%) consider violent crimes in the city to be extremely problematic. Following this, 34% of respondents view the situation as moderately problematic, while 20% see it as very much problematic. A smaller percentage, 7%, consider

violent crimes to be slightly problematic. No respondents indicated that violent crime is not at all problematic. Overall, these findings suggest that most of the 75 respondents acknowledge violent crime as a serious concern, albeit with varying levels of intensity.

Figure 11: Graphical representation of respondents according to their perception regarding violent crimes in the city

Contingency Table 1

Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents according to what extent do they believe rise in crime is primarily due to poverty

Victimization Status	Crime is caused by Poverty		Total
	Extremely / Very much	Moderately/ Slightly	
Not victimized	46	11	57
Victimized	10	8	18
TOTAL	56	19	75

Null Hypothesis (H₀): there is no significant relationship between victimization status and the belief that the crime is caused by poverty.

Degree of freedom:
df=(2-1)×(2-1) = 1

Alternative Hypothesis (H₁): there is a significant relationship between victimization status and belief that crime is caused by poverty.

Critical value:

The critical value of chi-square for 1 degree of freedom at a significance level of 0.05 (or 5%) is **3.841**

$$X^2 = \frac{(46-42.56)^2}{42.56} + \frac{(11-14.44)^2}{14.44} + \frac{(10-13.44)^2}{13.44} + \frac{(8-4.56)^2}{4.56}$$

Inference:

Since the calculated chi-square value (4.57) is greater than the critical value so we reject the null hypothesis which means there is a significant relationship between victimization status and the belief that crime is caused by poverty.

Sum:

$$X^2 = 4.57$$

Contingency Table 2

Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents according to how much unemployment and crime rate are related

Victimization Status	Crime is caused by Unemployment		Total
	Extremely related/ very related	Moderately related/ Slightly related	
Not victimized	47	10	57
Victimized	10	8	18
TOTAL	57	18	75

Null Hypothesis (H₀): there is no significant relationship between victimization status and the belief that the crime is caused by unemployment.

Alternative Hypothesis (H₁): there is a significant relationship between victimization status and belief that crime is caused by unemployment.

$$X^2 = \frac{(47-43.32)^2}{43.32} + \frac{(10-13.68)^2}{13.68} + \frac{(12-13.68)^2}{13.68} + \frac{(8-4.32)^2}{4.32}$$

Sum:

$$X^2 = 5.42$$

Degree of freedom:

$$df = (2-1) \times (2-1) = 1$$

Critical value:

The critical value of chi-square for 1 degree of freedom at a significance level of 0.05 (or 5%) is **3.841**

Inference:

Since the calculated chi-square value (5.42) is greater than the critical value so we reject the null hypothesis which means there is a significant relationship between victimization status and the belief that crime is caused by unemployment.

Contingency Table 3

Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents according to how important education is in reducing crime

Victimization Status	Crime is caused by lack of Education		Total
	Extremely important/very important	Moderately important/ Slightly important	
Not victimized	47	10	57
Victimized	12	6	18
TOTAL	59	16	75

Null Hypothesis (H₀): there is no significant relationship between victimization status and the belief that the crime is caused by lack of education.

Alternative Hypothesis (H₁): there is a significant relationship between victimization status and belief that crime is caused by lack of education.

$$X^2 = \frac{(47-44.84)^2}{44.84} + \frac{(10-12.16)^2}{12.16} + \frac{(12-14.16)^2}{14.16} + \frac{(6-3.84)^2}{3.84}$$

Sum:

$$X^2 = 2.03$$

Degree of freedom:

$$df = (2-1) \times (2-1) = 1$$

Critical value:

The critical value of chi-square for 1 degree of freedom at a significance level of 0.05 (or 5%) is **3.841**

Inference:

Since the calculated chi-square value (2.03) is less than the critical value so we fail to reject the null hypothesis which means there is no significant relationship between victimization status and the belief that crime is caused by lack of education.

Contingency Table 4

Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents according to what extent the drug use contributes to criminal activity

Victimization Status	Crime is caused by drug abuse		Total
	To an extreme extent/ very large extent	To a moderate extent/ slight extent	
Not victimized	41	16	57
Victimized	13	5	18
TOTAL	54	21	75

Null hypothesis (H₀): there is no significant relationship between victimization status and belief that the crime is caused by drug abuse.

Alternative hypothesis (H₄): there is a significant relationship between victimization status and belief that crime is caused by drug abuse.

$$X^2 = \frac{(41-41.04)^2}{41.04} + \frac{(16-15.96)^2}{15.96} + \frac{(13-12.96)^2}{12.96} + \frac{(5-5.04)^2}{5.04}$$

Sum:
X² = 0.00054

Degree of freedom:
df =(2-1)×(2-1) = 1

Critical value:
The critical value of chi-square for 1 degree of freedom at a significance level of 0.05 (or 5%) is **3.841**

Inference:
Since the calculated chi-square value (0.00054) is much less than the critical value so we fail to reject the null hypothesis which means there is no significant relationship between victimization status and the belief that crime is caused by drug abuse.

Contingency Table 5

Frequency and percentage distribution of respondents according to do they believe all these crimes are due to inadequate law enforcement

Victimization Status	Crime is caused by Inadequate law enforcement		Total
	Strongly agree /Agree	Neutral/Disagree	
Not victimized	51	6	57
Victimized	13	5	18
TOTAL	64	11	75

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Null Hypothesis (H₀): there is no significant relationship between victimization status and the belief that the crime is caused by inadequate law enforcement.

Alternative Hypothesis (H₅): there is a significant relationship between victimization status and belief that crime is caused by inadequate law enforcement.

$$X^2 = \frac{(51-48.6)^2}{48.64} + \frac{(6-8.36)^2}{8.36} + \frac{(13-15.36)^2}{15.36} + \frac{(5-2.64)^2}{2.64}$$

Sum:
X² = 3.25

Degree of freedom:
df =(2-1)×(2-1) = 1

Critical value:
The critical value of chi-square for 1 degree of freedom at a significance level of 0.05 (or 5%) is **3.841**

Inference:
Since the calculated chi-square value (3.25) is less than the critical value we fail to reject the null hypothesis which means there is no significant relationship between victimization status and the belief that crime is caused by inadequate law enforcement.

SUMMARY:
This thesis explores the views and opinions of the people living in Garhi Khairo, a town in Sindh's Jacobabad district, on public safety and crime. The main goal is to investigate how locals view crime, what influences their perceptions, and how their everyday lives and conduct are affected by fears of crime. Based on a survey of a representative sample of locals from various socioeconomic backgrounds, the study was carried out. Opinions on a range of common crimes in the community, including violent crime, robbery, and theft, are analyzed through a poll, and also conclusions on the efficiency of law

enforcement. The emotional and social impacts of crime on both the person and the community are also deeply studied in this research. The findings show that a huge majority of locals believe crime in Garhi Khairo is becoming a bigger problem. Factors such as unemployment, poverty, drug addiction, lack of education and inadequate law enforcement were cited as the main causes of the growing crime rates. The survey also shows that a large number of locals experience feelings of insecurity, especially at night and in public areas. As a result, they change their behavior, staying away from certain places and installing security systems in their homes, among other things.

FINDINGS:

Demographic Profile of Respondents

A total of 75 individuals from Garhi Khairo participated in the study. The age distribution shows that the largest group of respondents (28%) were aged 50 years or older, followed by 21% between 42 and 49 years. Respondents aged 26 to 33 years made up 20% of the sample, while 19% were between 34 and 41 years old. The youngest group, aged 18 to 25 years, constituted 12%. All participants were male; no other gender was included in the study.

Educational Background

The study primarily included individuals with at least an intermediate level of education. The majority of respondents (51%) held a graduate degree, 36% had completed intermediate education, and 13% held postgraduate qualifications. This educational profile may influence respondents' understanding and perceptions of the crime-related issues under investigation.

Employment and Occupational Status

Most respondents (60%) were employed at the time of the study, suggesting a strong representation from the working population. Additionally, 23% were unemployed, while 17% were self-employed. The occupational breakdown shows that teachers and unemployed individuals each made up 23% of the sample. Businessmen constituted 16%, while bankers and doctors each represented 13%, indicating participation from both the financial and healthcare sectors. Police personnel accounted for 8%, and farmers were the least represented at 4%.

This diverse occupational mix provided a broad range of perspectives for the study.

Income Distribution

Nearly half of the respondents (49%) reported a monthly income between PKR 50,000 and 100,000, making it the most common income bracket. About 27% earned less than PKR 50,000, while 17% had incomes exceeding PKR 100,000. Additionally, 23% reported no income, likely including students, unemployed individuals, or dependents. This distribution suggests a predominance of middle-income earners within the sample.

Concern about Crime Rate

The data indicates that the vast majority of respondents (74%) were extremely concerned about the crime rate in their city. A further 20% reported being very concerned, and 6% were moderately concerned. Notably, no respondents indicated being slightly or not at all concerned. This reflects a high level of anxiety regarding crime and underscores the urgency of addressing safety issues in Garhi Khairo.

Perception of Specific Crime Types

Respondents expressed varying levels of concern about different types of crime:

Property Crime: 40% perceived it as moderately problematic, 34% as extremely problematic, 14% as slightly problematic, and 12% as very much problematic. No one considered it not problematic.

Street Crime: 70% of respondents viewed it as extremely problematic, 14% as slightly problematic, 10% as very much problematic, and 6% as moderately problematic. No respondent reported it as not problematic.

Crime Against Individuals: 60% considered it extremely problematic, 28% very much problematic, 6% moderately problematic, and another 6% slightly problematic. Again, no respondent regarded it as not at all problematic.

Violent Crime: 39% perceived it as extremely problematic, 34% as moderately problematic, 20% as very much problematic, and 7% as slightly problematic. None viewed it as not at all problematic.

CONCLUSION:

The study concludes that individuals who have experienced victimization are more likely to associate crime with poverty and unemployment, indicating a perceived link between economic hardship and criminal behavior. However, no significant connection was found between victimization status and beliefs that crime stems from lack of education, drug abuse, or inadequate law enforcement. These findings suggest that socio-economic factors, particularly poverty and unemployment, are viewed as primary contributors to crime by those directly affected, whereas other commonly assumed causes may require reevaluation in the context of local perceptions.

RECOMMENDATION:

To enhance safety and security in Garhi Khairo, the following targeted interventions are recommended:

1. It may be beneficial to promote small businesses and cottage industries, particularly those related to agriculture and crafts, which are well-suited to the rural context of Garhi Khairo. Providing financial support to aspiring entrepreneurs could help stimulate local economic activity. Efforts to promote gender equality—by enabling women to participate in income-generating activities—could also contribute significantly to poverty reduction and community development.
2. Supporting small-scale enterprises and regional trades might help address unemployment in the area. Offering small loans or seed funding could encourage individuals to start farms, shops, or workshops. Complementing this with training programs—focused on entrepreneurship, customer engagement, and financial management—could increase the chances of sustainable livelihood creation.
3. Strengthening local law enforcement to curb drug trafficking could be an effective step toward improving community well-being. At the same time, organizing public awareness campaigns and educational sessions, especially for youth, might help reduce drug abuse. Engaging schools, local leaders, and health professionals in such initiatives may enhance their reach and impact.

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